

Contribution to the European Digital Health Summit in Madrid, November 2025***1. How can EU and national policies — such as NIS2 — help health organisations strengthen resilience, and what governance models are needed to balance innovation, data sharing, and cybersecurity?***

EU legislation on cybersecurity provides Member States with a wide degree of autonomy, so national legislation is crucial and each country is different. There is a multispeed Europe on cyber issues, with some countries taking the lead and others lagging behind, mostly due to differences in infrastructure, resources and expertise between Member States. As a result, countries with inadequate standards constitute weak links. Thus, there is a need to reinforce EU-level standards under the format of regulations instead of Directives such as NIS2, in order to reduce the risk of disparate standards across the EU.

Another problem is that EU legislation is too general since it aims to cover all critical sectors with, for instance, a total of 18 sectors covered by the second NIS Directive. Hence, it does not target the healthcare sector specifically. Although the EU has enacted laws focusing on the medical sector, these do not fully encompass cybersecurity, or at least not in the level of detail needed to provide appropriate protection; examples include the Medical Devices Regulation (MDR) and *In Vitro* Diagnostic Regulation (IVDR). For these reasons, national legislation must complement the more general EU laws by developing rules that specifically target cybersecurity in the healthcare sector. This is a critical distinction which requires designated cyber rules to provide adequate protection. It is essential not to over-regulate, in order to stimulate digital innovation which has been crucial to recent medical advances in the healthcare sector. At the same time, however, regulation is essential in order to protect hospitals and the healthcare sector from devastating cyberattacks. Hence, there is a need to find the right balance by evolving towards a governance model focused on ‘smart regulation’, which seeks to provide leaner and more targeted forms of regulation that aim to specifically address gaps in the healthcare sector such as cybersecurity.

2. How can the healthcare sector strengthen collaboration between IT security teams, clinicians and management so that cyber resilience is clearly understood as a patient safety issue, not just a technical concern?

Too often, cybersecurity is treated as a technical issue that does not concern either doctors or patients. This needs to change, since cyberattacks can now directly impact medical processes and patient welfare in detrimental ways. Training for doctors is essential, both in medical schools and re-training/re-skilling for practising doctors. Awareness campaigns are indispensable and must target not only doctors, but also the administration and management teams in hospitals so that they can work more effectively together.

3. How can health organizations embed cybersecurity into every stage of the patient’s journey, from registration and diagnostics to treatment, discharge and follow-up at home?

This is very challenging, but can be achieved by implementing cybersecurity-by-design in all medical devices, equipment and machinery. EU legislation such as the EU Cyber Resilience Act can be useful in this regard. Once again, training, education and awareness-raising are essential both for doctors and management teams; this can be achieved in medical schools and as part of compulsory hospital training for new and existing recruits in the administration.

4. *If a hospital wants to design a first phase cybersecurity director plan aligned with NIS2 and ISO 27001, what are the first practical steps? What should be critical in the first three months?*

Because NIS2 and EU legislation provide Member States with a high degree of autonomy, this will entail considerable variations from one Member State to another and very much depends on existing national legislation. The same can be said of ISO 27001, which consists of a series of voluntary international standards that are not always followed-up by adequate reviews or audits on a regular basis. This means that national legislation is key in terms of providing binding and enforceable cybersecurity rules in the healthcare sector. Moreover, the NIS2 Directive is very general in its scope since it covers 18 sectors, and the same is true of ISO 27001 which is not sector-specific in most cases. Thus, instead of looking specifically at NIS2 or ISO 27001, hospitals should seek to be aligned with fully adequate, binding and enforceable national rules.

In order to establish a first phase cybersecurity director plan, an immediate assessment of the level of cyber protection for all medical equipment and devices is essential. This should be conducted by an external and specialized entity to ensure impartiality. After identifying where the flaws are located, each and every compromised piece of equipment will require an update with the newest and latest cyber-protection software to shield the medical facility. Updates need to be made every month, in order to keep pace with the rapidly evolving cyberthreat landscape. Large portions of the medical equipment itself might need to be changed and upgraded, instead of relying on legacy equipment to save money; such equipment has long since lost its edge to counter cyber threats. All passwords should be updated and made more complex, with additional letters, numbers and symbols to reduce the risk of hacking. A system of passkeys should also be introduced whenever possible throughout medical systems and processes.

Specific reporting requirements under the NIS2 Directive make it essential for hospitals to bolster their existing IT team or create a new team of experts by hiring additional qualified staff, whose purpose will be to focus specifically on cybersecurity throughout hospital infrastructure. This IT team needs to create effective channels for close contact and regular exchange of cyber information with relevant national authorities identified by the NIS2 Directive, including the national Computer Security Incident Response Team (CSIRT), along with the Single National Point of Contact (SNPC). In cases of serious cyber breaches, the hospital IT team must also contact the relevant EU authorities, including ENISA and the NIS Cooperation Group.

5. *What lessons can we draw from other critical infrastructure sectors such as energy, transport or finance that could help healthcare improve its cyber preparedness and incident response?*

Many lessons can be drawn from the energy sector. First, the energy sector has underscored to what extent all critical infrastructure are interconnected, since a cyberattack originating in the energy sector can rapidly spread to all other sectors. Hence, it is essential for the healthcare sector to better secure its supply chains and reduce vulnerabilities stemming from linkages to other sectors. Second, the energy sector demonstrates to what extent EU Member States are interconnected, since a cyberattack originating in the energy sector of an Eastern European country, possibly due to the ongoing war in Ukraine, for example, can rapidly spread and propagate to all other Member States. Thus, it is essential for the EU to reinforce common EU-wide cyber standards to prevent the emergence of weak links, including the creation of sector-specific rules, instead of the currently general approach of the NIS-2 Directive.

6. *How can patients and civil society contribute to shaping more transparent and trusted cybersecurity practices? Are there concrete mechanisms, such as patient councils or public reporting that could be effective?*

Patient councils and public reporting are excellent ideas to better associate patients and civil society in shaping more transparent and trusted cybersecurity practices. Human error, negligence and lack of knowledge or training remain the most important causes of cybersecurity breaches. Thus, it is not enough to simply train doctors and management teams within hospitals; patients and citizens must also be made aware of cybersecurity risks. Patients can then better protect themselves when accessing and reviewing their private medical data and online information, where the risks of data theft or hacking are high due to inadequate personal passwords (rarely changed often enough). It is essential for citizens and patients to take responsibility for their own cybersecurity, working in close collaboration with doctors and the hospital administration who can guide them towards best practices and safe procedures.

7. *How do we balance the pressure for rapid digital transformation (AI, cloud, IOT-connected devices) with the obligation to maintain high levels of data protection and resilience? Where to draw the line when business wants to move faster than security?*

Digitization of the healthcare industry has brought many benefits across all domains, including new medical breakthroughs, more efficient treatment and better access to medical data/records both for doctors and patients. At the same time, the digital revolution is a double-edged sword, since it has also led to significant new cybersecurity risks. It is essential to balance the pressure from rapid digital transformation with the obligation to maintain high levels of data protection, which can be achieved by embedding ‘cybersecurity-by-design’ in all medical equipment and devices. The EU’s Cyber Resilience Act is also a positive step in the right direction, since it promotes the development of common cybersecurity standards for products that integrate digital components (mainly hardware and software), with binding rules for producers encompassing the design, deployment and maintenance of products. Another way to balance these competing imperatives is, once again, through generalized cybersecurity training and awareness raising not only for doctors and management teams, but also for patients and civil society. Lastly, the achievement of ‘smart’ and targeted regulation is also essential; policymakers need to evolve towards smarter, leaner and more targeted forms of regulation that specifically aim to address gaps in key sectors.

8. *What kind of public investment or EU-level support is needed to help smaller hospitals and regional health systems reach a basic level of cyber maturity without creating a two-speed Europe in terms of patient safety?*

Unfortunately, big hospitals in European capitals or large cities gather most of the funding, resources and infrastructure for healthcare services. We are already witnessing the emergence of a two-speed Europe with stark urban-rural contrasts, whereby rural areas suffer from “medical deserts”. Even within developed urban areas, notable disparities are apparent between large, sometimes private hospitals vs. smaller, public medical facilities, especially in poorer neighbourhoods. One way to address this is to provide more resources to the European Regional Development Fund, together with other frameworks which form part of European Structural and Investment Funds; these are charged with transferring resources from richer regions (not countries) to invest them in the infrastructure and services of underdeveloped regions. For instance, it would be useful to provide the European Regional Development Fund with a specific financial envelope for cyber security in the healthcare sector.

9. *If we agree that culture eats policy for breakfast, what does a strong cybersecurity culture look like in a hospital? What concrete behaviours should clinicians, administrative staff and technicians adopt in their day-to-day work?*

In terms of concrete behaviour, passwords should be changed on a regular basis, both for doctors and patients alike, especially when it comes to accessing personal and private healthcare data on patients. In addition to passwords with two-factor authentication (2FA), passkeys should be privileged whenever possible. While not yet perfect, passkey end-to-end encryption can be created on a device, in a password manager, or on a physical security key to reinforce security protections. Moreover, an immediate assessment of the level of cyber protection for all medical equipment is essential. Outdated software is a prime target for cybercriminals, as it often lacks the latest security patches, making it an easy gateway to penetrate the hospital network before propagating to infect the entire system.

10. *For letting the audience to reflect in one action they can take today to be more cyber resilient, what is the one recommendation you can make for a safer patient journey?*

For a safer patient journey, I would first recommend that all patients change their passwords immediately and make them more elaborate, and second that they investigate the use of passkeys. Other actions might include asking a doctor what precise cyber policies are in place to reduce cybersecurity risks in the office or medical facility; if inadequate, the patient should consider changing doctors.